

Assessing the impact of climate change on the Nypa Palm (*Nypa fruticosa*) and associated species of the Sundarbans mangrove of Bangladesh

Md. Mizanur Rahman

Information and Communication Technology Division, Bangladesh, E-mail:

rahmanboku@gmail.com

Abstract

The overarching objective of the study was to assess the impact of climate change on the *Nypa* Palm (*Nypa fruticosa*) and associated species of the Sundarbans mangrove of Bangladesh. Both primary and secondary data were used in this study. It was revealed that faster sedimentation degrades the habitat of the *Nypa*. The inland *Nypa* is being disappeared rapidly due to increased salinity. Salinity causes a major threat to the succession of *Nypa*. The salinity weakens the potentiality of natural regeneration by reducing the viability of seeds, seedling germination and seedling recruitment. The *Nypa* mortality rate is increased due to increased salinity. The production of new leaves, leaf longevity and the leaf area, net photosynthesis rate, stomata conductance and transpiration rate of leaves are being reduced. The changes in the composition and abundance of this sensitive indicator species provide the specific biological signal of the climate change impacts.

Keywords: *Nypa* Palm, Sundarbans Mangrove, Increased Salinity, Natural Regeneration, Indicator Species

Introduction

Golpata (*Nypa Palm*) is an indicator plant species of the Sundarbans biome albeit it is neither a true littoral nor a high saline resistant species (Rahman 2020; Rahman and Vacik 2014). It grows in the mudflat and fertile riparian habitats where the water slowly rises up and then slowly falls back again. It can grow inland where the tide deposits the seeds. The *Nypa* has various usages in our life (Hamilton and Murphy 1988).

Nypa can tolerate infrequent inundation, as long as the soil does not dry out. It occurs mostly in the fresh swamp and the mixed fresh-brackish swamp forests. It also grows on lowlands and depressions, at the base of eroding slopes and cliffs, or on sandy ridges or embankments of *Mongla*, *Rampal*, *Morelganj*, *Shoronkhola*, *Bagerhat Sadar*, *Koyra*, *Paikgachha*, *Dacope*, *Sheyamnagar*, *Ashashuni*, *Pirojpur Sadar*, *Mathbaria*, *Pathorghata*, *Khepupara*, *Galachipa* and *Amtali* Upazila. It is an undershrub in the riparian zones and the ecological climax of *Nypa* or its associates occurs in pure stands on islets in the main channels or on depressions of the interior river meanders having silt loam soil texture. These deposits are enriched frequently by floods or surface run-off from nearby rivers during the monsoon.

The feathery leaves of the *Nypa* look like the coconut leaves. They are used as a roofing material by the coastal inhabitants for their thatched houses and dwellings (Hossain and Islam 2015). The leaves are also widely used in the basket industry. A young leaf is used in the cigar industry to wrap the tobacco. It produces double biofuel compared to maize which is almost equal to sugarcane. The sap and the young fruits can be decomposed to produce biogas. Sometimes large stems are used as a life buoy in the water.

The sap of *Nypa* is fed to pigs to improve the flavour of the meat. The inflorescence is tapped to capture the sweet sap in the Patuakhali coastal areas. The collected sap is boiled down to produce jaggery and sweet syrup (gur). The sap is also used to produce a local alcoholic beverage called *Cholai Modh* (local liquor). Vinegar can be produced from this liquor by storing it for several weeks. Young shoots are consumed as a vegetable and the flower petals have aromatic value. Immature fruit is used to prepare desserts in many countries. The petals of the flower are also used as an aromatic tea.

They are important in preserving water quality and controlling river erosion. They provide a habitat for wildlife refuges, especially for amphibians and reptiles. It provides shelter, shade and food for many aquatic animals. *Nypa* increases biodiversity and provides wildlife corridors enabling aquatic and riparian organisms to move along river systems avoiding isolated communities. They provide forage for wildlife. It lowers nitrate contamination in surface runoff from agricultural fields. It works as windbreaks or shelterbelts to protect crops, water sources, soils and settlements. They are essential for dune stabilization as well. *Nypa* vegetation is the home of Crabs, Snails, Oysters, Mollusks, Brittle Star, Algae, Tortoises and Snakes. They provide excellent nurseries for shrimp, *Hilsha* Fish, Zebra Fish, Hamilton Fish, Asian Sea Bass, Black Sea Bass, Silver Pomfret, Crocodile and Dolphins. They are very important habitats for Fishing Cat, Bengal Monitor, Black Lizard, Yellow Monitor, Water Monitor, Grey Mongoose, Ring Lizard, Pangolin, and other threatened species. The Royal Bengal Tiger uses *Nypa* patches for resting, sleeping and dining spaces.

Bangladesh faces unpredictable climate change impacts for a long that is subject to multiple stressors originating from a rapidly changing environment (Rahman 2020, Rahman 2021a, Rahman 2022c, Rahman 2023) and social dynamics (Mitchell *et al.* 2015, Rahman *et al.* 2009, Rahman 2021b, Rahman 2022a, b).

Methodology

Both primary and secondary data were used for this study. The secondary data were collected from different academic sources to develop a conceptual framework. A focus group discussion was done incorporating the respondents from diverse stakeholders. A total of ten key informants were interviewed to understand the impact of climate change on the *Nypa* Palm, an indicator species of the Sundarbans mangrove of Bangladesh. Content analysis was done to analyze the data.

Impact of climate change on *Nypa*'s Community

The respondents opined that the biodiversity of Sundarbans is exposed to threats of deforestation and climate change impacts. The declining trend of *Nypa* is one of the major threats to the mangrove ecosystem. The abundance of *Nypa* depends largely on soil type, salinity, duration and frequency of inundation and accretion of silt. The environmental parameters with direct influences

on Sundarbans in terms of global climate change are sea-level rise, natural calamities like cyclones, rising temperature, salinity and drought.

The obvious impacts of relative sea-level rise in the ecosystems of Sundarbans are permanent inundation, salinization and coastal erosion. It was added that a one-metre rise in sea level will destroy the whole ecosystem of Sundarbans. *Nypa* vegetation will be submerged underwater. The shift in the position of the land/sea boundary in the Sundarbans territory is complicated by high sedimentation rates in some areas and extensive coastal erosion in others. The coastal sediments are mobilized by tides and currents to the canals and the rivers. High siltation occurs in the dry season due to the low flow of water. The water bodies are being silted quickly and the *Nypa* is losing its habitat day by day.

Nypa is very sensitive to hydrological conditions and occurs in areas of low water salinity. *Karamjal, Jongra, Mora Passur, Nandobala, Harbouria, Choraputia, Andharmanik, Tamulbunia, Supoti* and *Kochikhali* forest areas are considered the paradise habitats for *Nypa*. But declining trends in *Nypa* abundance have been observed in these areas over time. The inland *Nypa* is being disappeared rapidly. Due to increased salinity freshwater swamps are being converted into the mixed fresh-brackish swamp while mixed fresh-brackish swamp into the brackish swamp and brackish swamp into the mangrove scrub. The littoral forests are becoming degraded forests due to higher mortality caused by higher salinity. With this change in the vegetation type, the *Nypa* is being disappeared from the past mixed fresh-brackish swamp. Salinity causes a major threat to the succession of *Nypa*. Salinity weakens the potentiality of natural regeneration by reducing the viability of seeds, seedling germination and seedling recruitment. The *Nypa* mortality rate is being accelerated due to increased salinity. The production of new leaves, leaf longevity and the leaf area, net photosynthesis rate, stomata conductance and transpiration rate of leaves are being reduced. The changes in the composition and abundance of this sensitive indicator species provide the specific biological signal of the climate change impacts.

References

Hamilton, L.S., Murphy, D.H. Use and management of Nipa palm (*Nypa fruticans*, arecaceae): a review. *Econ Bot* **42**, 206–213 (1988). <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF02858921>

- Hossain and Islam (2015) Utilization of Mangrove Forest Plant: Nipa Palm (*Nypa fruticans* Wurmb.). *American Journal of Agriculture and Forestry*. Vol. 3, No. 4, pp. 156-160. doi: 10.11648/j.ajaf.20150304.16
- Mitchell, S. B., Jennerjahn, T. C., Vizzini, S., & Zhang, W. (2015). Changes to processes in estuaries and coastal waters due to intense multiple pressures—An introduction and synthesis. *Estuarine, Coastal and Shelf Science*, 156, 1–6.
- Rahman, M. (2021b). *Biologia Futura*: can co-management protect Saint Martin’s corals of Bangladesh? *Biologia Futura*, 72(4), 517-527. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42977-021-00101-4>.
- Rahman, M. M. (2021a). Achieving Sustainable Development Goals of Agenda 2030 in Bangladesh: the crossroad of the governance and performance. *Public Administration and Policy*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/PAP-12-2020-0056>
- Rahman, M.M (2022a) Is co-management a double-edged sword in the protected areas of *Sundarbans* mangrove? *Biol Philos* 37, 4 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10539-022-09836-3>.
- Rahman, MM & Vacik, H 2014 ‘Impact of climate change on the nipa palm of Sundarbans’, In: *Sustaining Forests, Sustaining People: The Role of Research*, XXIV IUFRO World Congress, 5-11 October 2014, Salt Lake City, USA.
- Rahman, MM (2020) Impact of increased salinity on the plant community of the *Sundarbans* Mangrove of Bangladesh. *COMMUNITY ECOLOGY* 21, 273–284. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42974-020-00028-1>.
- Rahman, MM (2022b) Effectiveness of the coastal and marine conservation initiatives in Bangladesh: analyzing the drawbacks of the legal, policy, and institutional framework, *Journal of the Indian Ocean Region*, 18:2, 149-172, DOI: [10.1080/19480881.2022.2111050](https://doi.org/10.1080/19480881.2022.2111050).
- Rahman, MM (2023) Impact of Climate Change on Saint Martin's Island of Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4397578>

Rahman, MM, Nishat. A & Vacik, H (2009) Anthropogenic disturbances and plant diversity of the Madhupur Sal forests (*Shorea robusta* C.F. Gaertn) of Bangladesh, International Journal of Biodiversity Science & Management, 5:3, 162-173, DOI: [10.1080/17451590903236741](https://doi.org/10.1080/17451590903236741).